

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL FEATURES OF MACULAR EDEMA TREATMENT IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS

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Annotation: Diabetic macular edema (DME) is the most common cause of vision loss in both type 1 (T1) and type 2 (T2) diabetes mellitus (DM). The reported incidence of DME varies greatly from 0 to 3% in newly diagnosed cases to 28-29% in chronic diabetic patients with more than 20 years of disease duration. Similarly, the reported incidence of DMO ranges widely from 0.8 to 7.5% The pathogenesis of DMO is complex and poorly understood.

Keywords: diabetic macular edema, diabetes mellitus, glycemic control

Introduction. It is well established that of the various risk factors, poor glycemic control increases the risk of DMD, and a large body of evidence supports the long-term positive effects of tight glycemic control in diabetic patients. Consequently, insulin is one of the most widely used hypoglycemic agents in all forms of DM [] with the advantage of improving glycemic control in addition to reducing the incidence of diabetes-related complications. However, insulin use can have unintended consequences, with reports of increased rates of cardiovascular events and colorectal cancer in patients receiving insulin therapy. There are also several reports of an increased risk of DME when insulin therapy is used in diabetic patients
Study objective: To investigate the epidemiologic features of macular edema treatment in patients with diabetes mellitus.

Materials and Methods: The work was conducted in the departments of ophthalmology and in the regional eye hospital of Andijan. 78 patients diagnosed with diabetic macular edema were under observation during the period from January 2020 to December 2022. Retrospective analysis of treatment results of patients with wet form of AMD who received more than 75 IVCs of ranibizumab as anti-angiogenic therapy was carried out. Two study groups consisted of 18 patients (eyes) aged 52 to 84 years, 45 women and 33 men. The mean age was 65 ± 5 years. All patients of the studied groups showed a pronounced positive dynamics during treatment with ranibizumab both in the phase of loading injections and during further treatment. All treated patients had relapses of the wet form of the disease in the form of decreased visual acuity and intra- and subretinal fluid accumulation.

Results of the research: dynamic observation after loading injections of aflibercept confirmed the increase ($2,1 \pm 0,2$ months) of the period of CNS activity suppression which allows to relieve the burden of treatment of a patient. Continued therapy with ranibizumab was accompanied by 4-week periods of decreased exudative activity followed by increased macular edema.

Conclusions: Anti-VEGF therapy has revolutionized the treatment of nVMD; however, despite remarkable visual benefits, significant gaps in efficacy remain. Not all patients respond to anti-VEGF therapy; these therapies

References:

1. Akramova D. et al. Stroke incidence and association with risk factors in women in Uzbekistan //Cerebrovascular Diseases. – Allschwilerstrasse 10, Ch-4009 Basel, Switzerland : Karger, 2017. – T. 43.
2. Bobomuratov T.A., Sharipova O.A., Akramova N.T. Assessing the impact of secondary prevention among boys with bronchiectasis and delayed pubertal development // Science and Innovations in the Globalized world. San Diego, 2016. Vol. 1. P. 114-119.
3. Khamdamov B.Z. Indicators of immunocytocine status in purulent-necrotic lesions of the lower extremities in patients with diabetes mellitus.//American Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences, 2020 10(7) 473-478 DOI: 10.5923/j.ajmm.2020.- 1007.08 10.
- 4.Khamdamov B.Z. Indicators of immunocytocine status in purulent-necrotic lesions of the lower extremities in patients with diabetes mellitus. American Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences, 2020 10 (7): 473-478 DOI: 10.5923/j.20201001.08
5. M. I. Kamalova, N.K.Khaidarov, Sh.E.Islamov, Pathomorphological Features of hemorrhagic brain strokes, Journal of Biomedicine and Practice 2020, Special issue, pp. 101-105
6. Kamalova Malika Ilkhomovna, Islamov Shavkat Eriyigitovich, Khaidarov Nodir Kadyrovich. Morphological Features Of Microvascular Tissue Of The Brain At Hemorrhagic Stroke. The American Journal of Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research, 2020. 2(10), 53-59
7. Khodjueva D. T., Khaydarova D. K., Khaydarov N. K. Complex evaluation of clinical and instrumental data for justification of optimal treatment activities in patients with resistant forms of epilepsy. American Journal of Research. USA. № 11-12, 2018. C.186-193.
8. Khodjueva D. T., Khaydarova D. K. Clinical and neurophysiological characteristics of post-insular cognitive disorders and issues of therapy optimization. Central Asian Journal of Pediatrics. Dec.2019. P 82-86